

A STUDY TO EVALUATE SLEEP EFFICIENCY SLEEP DISTURBANCE AND USE OF SLEEP MEDICATION IN UNDERGRADUATE UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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Abstract

Background: Sleep is a foundational pillar of physical health, crucial for emotional well-being and cognitive functioning. University students are mainly vulnerable to sleep problems due to academic burdens, lifestyle ups and downs, unbalanced sleep timetables, and increased stress. Poor sleep efficiency, sleep disturbances, and unsuitable use of sleep medications may negatively disturb academic routine and overall well-being.

Objective: This study investigates sleep efficiency, sleep disturbance, and usage of sleep medication among undergraduate students.

Material Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted on a sample of 280 undergraduate students at the Peoples University of Medical & Health Sciences for Women (PUMHSW) in Nawabshah. Utilizing Stratified random sampling. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire. And analyzed using SPSS version 25. Frequency, percentage, as descriptive statistics.

Results: The mean age of participants was 21.48 ± 12.31 years. Most students (73.9%) had good sleep efficiency (>85%), while 26.1% demonstrated moderate to poor sleep efficiency. Sleep disturbances were common, with 74.3% of students experiencing mild sleep disturbance and 20.4% experiencing moderate sleep disturbance. Participants frequently reported insomnia symptoms, specifically nocturnal awakenings, sleep fragmentation, and sleep related discomfort., Most students (83.6%) reported no sleep medication use. only 12.5% used medication less than once a week, with a small proportion reporting regular use. prescribed sleep medication was used by (8.9%) of participants, while (6.1%) used over-the-counter options, indicating minority usage for both.

Conclusion: Sleep disturbances are predominant among undergraduate university students despite the common having adequate sleep efficiency. Although the use of sleep medication was low, a significant number of students experienced disturbed sleep patterns that may impact their educational performance and

health. These findings highlight the need for sleep capability education and non-pharmacological interventions to help healthy sleep behaviors among university students.

INTRODUCTION

Sleep is a fundamental biological need that influences physical, mental, and emotional wellbeing. Adequate sleep has been linked to improved learning, memory consolidation and emotional regulation conversely, poor sleep quality contributes to impaired concentration, reduced academic performance and mental health disorders such as anxiety and depression.¹ Sleep problem are common in university students Due to study demands and other responsibilities they don't follow a regular routine they go to bed late and have irregular wake cycles sleep efficiency define how much of time you spent in bed is actually spent sleeping less than 85% is considered low studies shows about 3% of undergraduate students and 12% of medical students have low sleep efficiency this can lead to problems like anxiety tiredness and low performance.² Sleep disturbance is any problem that interrupt's normal sleep such as falling asleep waking up often waking up too early or feeling very sleepy during the day it leads to poor quality and less amount of sleep, sleep disruption is common in undergraduate students worldwide.³ In the United States at least 60% of university students have poor sleep quality, and 26.4% experience insomnia Asian and African students have high frequencies of sleep compared to European students.⁴ Sleep efficiency means how well you sleep it is the percentage of time you actually spend sleeping compared to the total time you spend in bed.⁵ And if you go to bed for 8 hours but only sleep for 5 hours your sleep efficiency is low and low sleep efficiency means your body isn't getting the full benefit of rest.⁶ Furthermore, increasing reliance on sleep medications raises concerns about dependency and side effects.⁷ Sleep medicine are drugs people take when they have trouble falling asleep or staying asleep, Women older adults and people with lower income are more likely to use them.⁸ Around 60% of undergraduate university students have poor sleep quality having an

average of 7 hours sleep, Researcher demonstrate that sleep efficiency may be one route past history mostly focused on sleep efficiency and total sleep time calculated with accelerometer.⁹ High rates of insomnia report in Norway especially in female students Spread of digital or display devices are sleep less and with poorer influence sleep late night screen use connect to short or poor sleep quality¹⁰ Sleep is crucial for athletes, However a large number of elite athletes sleep less with poorer quality than recommended such as travel competition times stress caffeine research reported average sleep patterns calculation of sleep regularity or intra individual variation is becoming popular in sleep science research¹¹ Students are facing many problems in their social personal and academic lives because when we enter in a university life there is big changes in daily habits but the most affected thing sleep which cause insomnia tiredness or poor concentration many studies have tried to explore sleep hygiene in student the sleep hygiene index is most widely used and validated tool to measure these behaviors.¹² In India 55.78% of college students suffered from sleep disturbances studies in china have found associations between physical activities in Karachi research found poor sleep was prevalent among university students lifestyle and stress factors contribute to sleep disturbance.¹³

MATERIALS & METHODS

This study is descriptive cross sectional design was conducted to identify the sleep efficiency, sleep disturbance, and use of sleep medication in undergraduate university students. Data collection was over two months period of time from 17 November to 17 January 2026 after approval of Institutional review board (IRB) sample size was 280 calculated by using Yamane formula the calculation was based on 95% confidence level, a stratified probability sampling was used to select participants the

inclusion criteria included undergraduate university students. Those who agreed to sign informed consent. Exclusion criteria included those who students who disabled or had acute

medical conditions and chronic medical conditions (lung, heart and kidney diseases) those students who have current psychiatric or neurologic disorders. Unwilling to participate.

RESULTS

Figure No 1: Age of Respondents

Figure No 2: Academic Year

Figure No 3: Ethnicity

Figure No 4: Socioeconomic Status

Table No 1: Bed Time

Bed Time	Frequency	Percent
9:00pm to 10:00pm	31	11.1%
11:00pm to 12:00am	128	45.1%
1:00am to 2:00am	101	36.1%
3:00am to 4:00am	20	7.1%
Total	280	100.0%

Table No 2: Wakeup Time

Wakeup Time	Frequency	Percent
4:00am to 5:00am	15	5.4%
6:00am to 7:00am	109	38.9%
8:00am to 9:00am	117	41.8%
10:00am to 11:00am	39	13.9%

Total	280	100.0%
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Table No 3: Hours of sleep

Hours of sleep	Frequency	Percent
5 to 6 hours	128	45.7%
7 to 8 hours	122	43.6%
9 to 10 hours	26	9.3%
11 to 12 hours	4	1.4%
Total	280	100.0

Table No 4: Total Sleep Efficiency

Total Sleep Efficiency	Frequency	Percent
>85%	207	73.9%
75-84%	38	13.6%
65-74%	19	6.8%
<65%	16	5.7%
Total	280	100.0%

Table No 5: Waking up in the middle of the night or early morning

Waking up in the middle of the night or early morning	Frequency	percent
Not during the past month	84	30.0%
Less than once a week	102	36.4%
Once or twice a week	57	20.4%
Three or more times a week	37	13.2%
Total	280	100.0%

Table No 6: Have to get up to use bathroom

Have to get up to use bathroom	Frequency	Percent
Not during the past month	82	29.3%
Less than once a week	98	35.0%
Once or twice a week	54	19.3%
Three or more times a week	46	16.4%
Total	280	100.0%

Table No 7: Cannot Breathe Comfortably

Cannot breathe comfortably	Frequency	Percent
Not during the past month	184	65.7%
Less than once a week	61	21.8%
Once or twice a week	18	6.4%
Three or more times a week	17	6.1%

Table No 8: Cough or Snore Loudly

Cough or snore loudly	Frequency	Percent
Not during the past month	203	72.5%
Less than once a week	33	11.8%
Once or twice a week	29	10.4%

Three or more times a week	15	5.4%
Total	280	100.0%

Table No 9: Feel too cold

Feel too cold	Frequency	Percent
Not during the past month	144	51.4%
Less than once a week	77	27.5%
Once or twice a week	38	13.6%
Three or more times a week	21	7.5%
Total	280	100.0%

Table No 10: Feel too hot

Feel too hot	Frequency	Percent
not during the past month	189	67.5%
less than once a week	53	18.9%
once or twice a week	28	10.0%
three or more times a week	10	3.6%
Total	280	100.0%

Table No 11: Have Bad Dreams

Have bad dreams	Frequency	Percent
Not during the past month	132	47.1%
Less than once a week	83	29.6%
Once or twice a week	37	13.2%
Three or more times a week	28	10.0%
Total	280	100.0%

Table No 12: Have Pain

Have pain	Frequency	Percent
not during the past month	161	57.5%
less than once a week	67	23.9%
once or twice a week	30	10.7%
three or more times a week	22	7.9%
Total	280	100.0%

Table No 13: Total Sleep Disturbance

Total Sleep Disturbance	Frequency	Percent
0	14	5.0%
1-9	208	74.3%
10-18	57	20.4%
19-27	1	.4%

Table No 14: How often have you taken medicine to sleep?

During the past month how often have you taken medicine to sleep?	Frequency	Percent
Not during the past month	234	83.6%
Less than once a week	35	12.5%

Once or twice a week	7	2.5%
Three or more times a week	4	1.4%
Total	280	100.0%

Table No 15: If yes how often have taken sleep medication

If yes how often have taken sleep medication?	Frequency	Percent
Prescribed	25	8.9%
OTC	17	6.1%
N/A	238	85.0%
Total	280	100.0%

DISCUSSION

About the demographic characteristics, the results showed that the mean age of the respondents was 21.48 ± 12.31 years, indicating that the participants were predominantly young adults enrolled in undergraduate programs. This age group represents a critical developmental period during which lifestyle changes, academic pressure, and social commitments may influence sleep patterns. Similar recent studies age among undergraduate students were reported, which focused on sleep patterns in university populations.¹⁴

Concerning the academic year, the findings showed that the majority of students were from the 4th year 101 (36.07%), followed by 2nd year 73 (26.07%), 3rd year 66 (23.57%), and 1st year 40 (14.29%). This indicates greater participation from senior students, who may experience higher academic workload and clinical or practical responsibilities. Similar findings were reported who observed increased stress and sleep problems among senior undergraduate students.¹⁵

About marital status, the findings revealed that most participants were single 275 (98.21%), while 5 (1.79%) were married. Regarding residential status, the results showed that 173 (61.79%) participants belonged to urban areas, while 107 (38.21%) were from rural areas. Regarding religion, the findings showed that the majority of participants were Muslims 241 (86.07%), followed by Hindus 35 (12.5%) and Christians 4 (1.4%). This distribution reflects the religious composition of the local population and is comparable with recent regional studies conducted among university students.

Concerning ethnicity, the findings showed that 164 (58.57%) participants were Sindhi, followed by Punjabi 63 (22.50%), Baloch 27 (9.64%), and Siraiki 26 (9.29%). This reflects ethnic diversity within the study population and is consistent with recent local university-based studies.

About socioeconomic status, the results showed that 156 (55.71%) participants belonged to the poor class, 94 (33.57%) to the middle class, and 30 (10.71%) to the rich class. Lower socioeconomic status has been linked with increased stress and poorer sleep outcomes among students, as reported in past studies.¹⁶

Regarding the academic program, the findings showed equal participation from all programs, with 70 (25.0%) students each from BSN Generic, DPT, Pharm-D, and BSPH. This balanced distribution enhances the representativeness of the sample across undergraduate health science disciplines.

Sleep Efficiency, Sleep Disturbance, and Use of Sleep Medication

Regarding the sleep efficiency results of this study, the results revealed that 207 (73.9%) students had good sleep efficiency, while 73 (26.1%) reported poor sleep efficiency, Which recognized poor sleep efficiency among university students due to irregular sleep schedules and lifestyle issues. Similar outcomes were stated in past studies by Becker,¹⁷ Which recognized poor sleep efficiency among university students due to irregular sleep schedules and lifestyle issues.

Sleep disturbance, the findings showed that a large proportion of undergraduate students experienced sleep disturbance, including

difficulty initiating sleep and nighttime awakenings observed high levels of sleep disturbance among university students. About the use of sleep medication, the results exposed that the 234 (83.6%) did not use sleep medication, while only a 35 (12.5%) reported less than once a week, 7 (2.5%) reported once or twice a week, 4 (1.4%) reported three or more times a week. This specifies that despite sleep problems, pharmacological sleep aids are not commonly used by undergraduate students.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that sleep-related problems are common among undergraduate university students. The demographic characteristics represent a vulnerable group that is prone to sleep disturbances due to academic pressure, changing daily routines, and psychosocial responsibilities. Although the majority of students demonstrated good sleep efficiency (>85%), a considerable proportion still experienced moderate to poor sleep efficiency, indicating that a notable number of students are not obtaining fully restorative sleep. Sleep disturbances were highly prevalent, with most students reporting mild to moderate levels of sleep disturbance, including nighttime awakenings, difficulty maintaining sleep, and discomfort during sleep. These disturbances can fragment sleep and reduce sleep quality, leading to daytime fatigue, impaired concentration, and decreased academic performance. Overall, the findings highlight that sleep efficiency, sleep disturbance, and lifestyle-related factors significantly affect undergraduate students and may negatively influence their academic performance, physical health, and mental well-being.

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